

Effect of Yoga Practicing on Spiritual Intelligence of Undergraduate Students

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Abstract

This study was conducted to see the effect of practicing yoga on the spiritual intelligence of 80 undergraduate students were selected using the purposive sampling method from Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya, Haridwar. The sample comprises both regular yoga practitioners (those who have practiced for at least two years) and non-practitioners. The data were gathered using the Spiritual Intelligence Scale (SIS), developed by Dr. K.S. Mishra. This scale is made up of 42 statements that serve as indicators of spiritual issues. The data were statistically assessed and a statistically significant difference was seen between yoga practitioners and non-practitioners of yoga on their spiritual intelligence. However, T-test results indicate no significant difference in spiritual intelligence between male and female students. Yoga assumes a paramount position in the prognostication and elucidation of spiritual intelligence.

Introduction

"*adhyavasayah buddhih*" (Sa.da.2/13). The ability that decides to do any work is called intelligence. The "Adhyvasayo" phrase is used to describe the capacity for making decisions; because of its determination-making quality, it is called "Budhhi". According to the tenets of Samkhya philosophy, the concept of 'intelligence' is synonymous with the term 'mahattatva'. According to Ayurveda, the intellect (Buddhi) is a separate entity from the mind (also known as Manas); however, the two operate together. According to the Charaka Samhita, there are six unique aspects of intellect, each of which relates to a different subject: 1. Chakshurbuddhi 2. Sparshanbuddhi 3. Rasanbuddhi 4. Shrotbuddhi 5. Ghranabuddhi 6. Manobuddhi.

The traditional conception of intelligence (i.e., intelligence quotient) has been a key idea in the world. There is a common misconception that having a high IQ is important for living a happy and fulfilling life. Although IQ is a crucial component of how each person functions, it does not fully capture the richness of human intelligence (Sternberg, 1988). Other types of intelligence have grown in acceptance over the past few decades, and hypotheses of many multiple types of intelligence have received increased notoriety (Gardner, 1983). One's capacity to interact with others in a social situation is referred to as social intelligence (Goleman, 2006). Salovey *et al.* (2000) classified emotional intelligence as a subset of social intelligence. Zohar and Marshall (2000) defined spiritual intelligence as the ultimate intelligence. Spiritual

intelligence concerns the inner life of mind and spirit and its relationship to being in the world (Vaughn, 2002). These multiple types of intelligence, such as emotional, social, and spiritual intelligence, offer a more comprehensive picture of human intellect and have been favourably associated with measures of wellbeing (Raina, 2018; Khosravi & Nikmanesh, 2014; Singh and Sinha, 2013; Ebrahimi *et al.*, 2012).

One of the key factors in advancing personally, professionally, and academically is intelligence, which includes a variety of aspects and categories. Nowadays, a person's intelligence to maintain excellent physical, mental, social, and spiritual health has been compromised by modern lifestyle factors such as contaminated junk food, erratic sleeping schedules, and a lack of exercise. Many of these myths, such as the idea that eating almonds or walnuts boosts IQ, are widespread in society. Currently, different foods and medications are advertised as having the ability to boost IQ. Everybody wants to experience bliss for as long as possible. Yoga is an old Indian tradition that has provided man with the answers to his quest for optimal health and well-being on a spiritual and holistic level (Patil, 2020; Kumar *et al.*, 2019, Govindaraj *et al.*, 2016; Trakroo *et al.*, 2013). Research on yoga practise indicates a positive effect on several aspects of spirituality and spiritual intelligence (Csala *et al.*, 2021; Tapariya, 2021; Naik and Jabeen, 2019; Pandey, 2017). Yet, spirituality and spiritual intelligence are still largely unexplored fields in yoga study. The objective of this research is to investigate the impact of Yoga practise on the Spiritual Intelligence of undergraduate students.

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Yoga

The maxims of healthy living are one of India's enormous gifts to the world, fueled by yoga's philosophy. Yoga is primarily a spiritual practice that focuses on achieving harmony between the body and mind. It is based on a very delicate science. It is both an art and a science to live healthily. (Basavaraddi, n.d.). The etymology of the word "yoga" can be traced back to its Sanskrit root "yuj", which connotes the process of unifying or harnessing. This term is commonly associated with integrating the individual self with the universal consciousness.

Per the teachings of Panini, the term 'Yoga' can be traced back to its etymological origins from the root 'yuj', which connotes the state of concentration or deep samadhi, and 'yujir', which pertains to the act of joining, as per the principles laid down by Panini, the designation 'Yogi' signifies a person who assiduously practises the observance of spiritual rigours. When Patanjali discusses Yoga, he uses the term 'yuj', another term for 'samadhi', to describe it.

The science of yoga was systematically given by the great saint Patanjali in the form of 195 aphorisms called "Sutras". As stated in 'yama niyama asana pranayama pratyahara dharana dhyana samadhyo-a-shtavaangani' (Y.S. 2/29), the eightfold path outlined by Patanjali consists of social and ethical practises (Yama & Niyama), various postures (Asana), breathing exercises (Pranayama), Pratyahara, Dharna, meditation techniques (Dhyana) and Samadhi. The practice of yoga is believed to promote physical, and mental well-being and is a popular way for persons to connect with their inner selves and God. Yoga practice has multiple perspectives; however, it can be broadly classified into the following: Raja yoga, Hatha yoga, Jnana yoga, Tantra yoga, Bhakti yoga, Karma yoga, Ashtanga yoga, and Mantra yoga.

According to the yoga concept, the mind and body are not two distinct things, but rather two parts of a whole. This suggests that we can train the mind by concentrating on particular bodily functions, and vice versa. Introspection, like the niyama and swadhyaya from Patanjali's Yoga Sutras, indicates that we study our actions, thoughts, and behaviours to align our hearts and minds with spiritual principles, for only then can we take wise action (YS 2/32).

Spiritual Intelligence

The word spiritual intelligence has gained popularity in recent decades, as people hunt to understand and grow their inner selves beyond the traditional measures of

intelligence. It is the inherent inner ability of the human brain and mind that draws its most profound resources from the centre of the cosmos. The ability of the brain to discover and use meaning in problem-solving has evolved over millions of years (Zohar & Marshall, 2000). It is an ability to comprehend and access a deeper level of consciousness, and to use that understanding to guide one's thinking, decision, emotions, perception, and behaviour.

The notion of spiritual intelligence has been explicated by Maharshi Patanjali in the Patanjali yoga sutra as "ritambhara pragya" as evidenced by the sutras "rtam-bhara tatra prajña" (Y.S.1/48). The Sanskrit expressions "Ritambhara" denoting the presence of a higher truth, "Tatra" indicating a specific location, and "Prajna" signifying knowledge, wisdom, and insight, hold significant meaning. Ritambhara Pragya is a form of intelligence that a yogi acquires after obtaining adhyatma-prasad. It is the purest and highest form of Wisdom. As per the Yoga Sutras, the Ritambhara pragya, or intellect, is concerned with a specific subject matter that cannot be obtained through sensory perception, verbal communication, or logical deduction, as stated in the following sutra: "shrutanumanaprajnabhyam anyavishayaa vishesharthatvat" (Y.S.1/49).

Spiritual intelligence integrates spirituality with intellectual components within a new structure (Emmons, 2006). The key components of spiritual intelligence are about cultivating a sense of compassion and empathy towards oneself and others, and experiencing that we are all interconnected. It is all about being in touch with one's the inner self and spirit and refining a sense of meaning in life (Kadkhoda & Jahani, 2012). This can lead to a stronger sense of inner peace as well as a good relationship with others and a deeper sense of meaning in life. According to Zohar and Marshall (2000), spiritual intelligence is the capacity to address and resolve issues of meaning and value, the intelligence that enables us to situate our lives and actions in a wider, richer context that provides meaning.

Spiritual intelligence is an umbrella term that encompasses the love of life, trust, insight, awareness of spirit and gratitude etc. Amram (2009) has categorised spiritual intelligence into seven main categories. These are inner-directedness, consciousness, grace, meaning, truth, peaceful surrender to self and transcendence. It is not limited to any certain religion, caste, and gender or belief system.

Relevant Literature

According to Maharshi Patanjali yoga sutra,

'nirvicharavaisharadye adhyatmaprasadah' (Y.S.1/47), spirituality becomes prasad and wisdom of rightness becomes ritambhara when the yogi achieves pure sattvic wisdom, also known as Vaishardya, which is free from rajoguna and tamoguna. This is possible when one practises yoga and reaches nirvichara samadhi. In this stage yogi's mind becomes clear and completely pure. This is known as adhyatma-prasad. The kind of intelligence that a yogi gets after attaining adhyatma-prasad is called Ritambhara Pragyā (Y.S.1/48). Ritambhara Pragyā means the one who holds the truth. Another facet of spiritual intelligence is transcendental consciousness. Yoga cultivates a favourable environment for transcendental consciousness by encouraging individuals to practise deeper attention (King, 2007).

The ultimate goal of all yogis is to achieve salvation, also known as Moksha, or to experience cosmic awareness, transcendental illumination or samadhi, in this world (Dean, 1965). Tapariya, (2021) found in his study that Yoga practitioners have high-level spiritual intelligence (Benevolence and optimism Dimensions) than that of non-Yoga Practiser. Several researchers (Seena *et al.*, 2017; Safara & Ghasemi, 2017; Mittal & Akhtar, 2011) revealed that doing yoga for a long time at least six months improves one's emotional intelligence as well as spiritual intelligence. A study by Safara (2017) on the Tehran Flight Control Center's air traffic controllers revealed that yoga exercises had a significant impact on the subjects' spiritual intelligence and their constituents (personal meaning production, critical thinking, transcendental consciousness and, expanded state of consciousness).

Research on yoga has become extremely popular during the last two decades. Various yoga exercises have been recommended to maintain one's blood pressure, improve constipation, insomnia, headache, arthritis, and asthma in addition to reducing anxiety and stress. (Pal & Dey, 2022; Banerjee, 2014; Gururaja, *et al.*, 2011; Shapiro *et al.*, 2007; Muktibodhananda, 1993). Daily yoga practice promotes flexibility, strength, endurance, and friendliness while cultivating more self-control, endurance, and compassion. It also promotes a sense of tranquilly and well-being (Collins, 1998; McCall, 2007).

The review focused on yoga's key elements, correlations, and connections to spiritual intelligence. Spirituality and the practice of yoga are strongly related.

Spiritual intelligence, in contrast to IQ, is something that can be developed and raised, and it is not restricted by age, gender, or race (Sohrabi, 2008). In the field of education, Spiritual intelligence integrates adaptability and emotional fortitude and is essential for assisting students and teachers in developing goals and ideals and making sense of their surroundings (Zohar & Marshall, 2001).

Research Method

The present study is an ex-post facto comparative research study that aims to explore the impact of Yoga practice on the Spiritual Intelligence of undergraduate students. The investigation was carried out on a sample of 80 undergraduate students selected from Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya located in Haridwar. The study was made up of two groups: a cohort of 40 third-year yoga students who had consistently engaged in yoga practise for a period of two years and a control group consisting of 40 third-year Bachelor of Arts students from the language department who did not engage in yoga practise. Students who suffered from any kind of severe mental and physical sickness were not allowed to enrol. The study's participants of both genders were chosen using purposive sampling.

Data Collection

Spiritual Intelligence Scale (SIS) developed by Dr. K.S. Mishra, was used for data collection. This scale consists of 42 statements which indices of spiritual matters. A five-point response mode was used as strongly agree, agree, Undecided, disagree and strongly disagree. The responses are scored by awarding 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1. It is equally valid for males and females. SIS has a total of 42 items to answer and there is no fixed time limit to complete.

Surveys were conducted in parallel to gauge participants' spiritual intelligence. The demographic information was first obtained from the respondents. The test is fully self-administered; however, the instructions were read out loud and explained. There was a strong rapport built up, and all scepticism was dispelled beforehand.

Result of the study

The findings obtained from the statistical analysis are as follow:

Table 1: Yoga practitioner and non-practitioner test scores

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)
Non-Yoga Practitioner	40	150.20	23.32	78	-6.65	.000
Yoga Practitioner	40	180.70	17.23			

Table 2: Male and female test scores

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)
Male	40	167.90	20.16	78	.858	.004*
Female	40	163.00	29.98			

*Not-significant

The results table 1 displays the Mean and Std. Deviation for each group followed by the t-value. When yoga practitioner and non-practitioner test scores were compared to assess any difference, the yoga practitioner mean scores show a significant difference of 180.70 from the Non-Yoga Practitioner mean scores 150.20 and changes were statistically significant. The mean of the yoga practitioner has pegged at a higher level than the non-yoga practitioner. Hence, it can be safely concluded that there is a statistically significant impact of yoga practice on spiritual intelligence of students. On the other hand, in table number 2 the findings indicate that there is a lack of substantial disparities in spiritual intelligence between male and female students.

Discussion on the findings

The investigation's findings showed that practising yoga had a considerable impact on spiritual intelligence. However, the findings of this study indicate that gender does not serve as a decisive determinant of spiritual intelligence. In line with the findings of this study, other researchers Kumar and Singh (2018); Seena *et al.* (2017); and Mittal and Akhtar (2011) have demonstrated that engaging in yoga practice for a minimum of six months can enhance an individual's spiritual intelligence. In his research, Tapariya (2021) discovered that yoga practitioners had higher levels of spiritual intelligence (Benevolence and Optimism Dimensions) than non-yoga practitioners. There are various paths to enhance spiritual intelligence, including Yoga, meditation, prayer, and connecting with nature (King, 2008). According to the research of Kadkhoda and Jahani (2012), this is all about gaining a more profound understanding of one's own significance and existence. Yoga has been associated with the development of a greater sense of inner tranquility, enhanced interpersonal connections, and a more profound sense of life's purpose. These exercises can benefit to calm the mind and foster a deeper sense of consciousness and inner peace. According to Safara and Ghasemi (2017) research, yoga has a significant impact on an individual's spiritual intelligence, specifically in critical thinking, personal meaning, expanded consciousness, and transcendental consciousness. Becker, (2000) claim that yoga exercises are effective on self-consciousness and

a powerful tool for enhancing one's belief in the significance of life and in the Creator. These findings have significant ramifications for both academic institutions and the study of spiritual intelligence.

Conclusion

The aim of the current study was to assess the variations in spiritual intelligence between individuals who engage in the practice of yoga and those who do not. The research findings evinced a notable difference in Spiritual Intelligence between practitioners of Yoga and individuals who do not practise Yoga. The cohort of individuals who engage in the practice of yoga exhibited a notably elevated degree of spiritual intelligence in contrast to those who do not engage in such activities. The findings of this investigation indicate the significance of promoting the adoption of yoga as a means of attaining a wholesome and purposeful existence.

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